

Galaxy User Research Report

Objectives

The objective of this UX research is to create a baseline for how our users move not only through Galaxy AU, but what touchpoints exist before and after. This exercise will allow us to understand motivations, pain points and tasks that users engage with as they use Galaxy Australia. We will use two UXR methods; User journey mapping and surveying to achieve our objective. We aim to present our findings back to internal stakeholders and Galaxy main, which will assist with the UI/UX working groups in terms of decision making.

This is a high level workflow devised by the Australian Biocommons. This was used in the user journey mapping process to prompt participants to explain each stage of their research or work flow.

Interpretation of these stages was up to the participant, this ensured we did not lead their answer, and kept the responses open.

Identified team issues

Before embarking on the user journey mapping and UX questionnaire I asked the team what they thought were pain points and areas for improvement in Galaxy Australia. This helps frame issues, as well as test our assumptions of what we think and what users tell us about our service.

recent pull request to Galaxy core for Name propagation

organising data in Galaxy.

Community

Menu Nav

unclear top menu tabs - eg one is "workflows", but there are more wfs in "shared data"

Having two separate menus for Galaxy main and galaxy GMS is confusing.

History Panel

Poor traceback of data in history analysis

Tool Discovery

Better tool search/navigation UI to suit 1000s of tools

broken connection to Tool Registry Service (TRS), which prevents browsing of available workflows via GA

Que time and feedback

Error alerts

Tool bar

Broken tools (am doing a bit of a test of "Get Data" tools - can present at a mtg perhaps my thoughts)

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Learning resources

Need to better automate /systematise testing of all Galaxy GTN tutorials on Galaxy Au (mostly good - some issues - this might be v difficult)

I think we should put our own Galaxy Au help pages somewhere we can access / add to / promote (currently have a few pages on Aus biocomms help pages but I have so much content I want to add - easier if we control directly)

Acknowledgement

wish I could rename job outputs when I run a tool (can do if it's in a wf)

Workflow Execution

It really bugs me that the Play button is furthest right. I think it should be furthest left or just right of workflow name

lifemonitor for galaxy workflow testing

Poor exposure of shared/community workflows

User Journey Mapping

Definition: A journey map is a visualization of the process that a person goes through in order to accomplish a goal. (Nielsen Norman Group, 2018)

User Journey Mapping is a technique used in UX (User Experience) design to understand the experience of a user as they interact with a product or service. It involves creating a visual representation of the various touchpoints and emotional states a user goes through from the moment they become aware of a solution to when they achieve their goal. The objective of user journey mapping is to identify pain points and areas for improvement in the user experience, and to design solutions that enhance the overall journey for the user. The end result of user journey mapping is a visual story that helps UX designers, product managers, and stakeholders to empathize with the user and make informed decisions.

Example User Journey map which demonstrates method applied.

Participants

We recruited participants from bioinformatics, life sciences, a PHD student and e-research analysts and interviewed 5 people.

Below are the high level characteristics of our user journey mapping participants.

Role: Bioinformatician	Role: E- research Analyst	Role: Bioinformatician	Role: Computational Biologist	Role: PhD student
<p>Organization: QCIF</p> <p>Gender: Female</p> <p>Specialization: Single Cell Genomics</p>	<p>Organization: University of the Sunshine Coast</p> <p>Gender: Female</p> <p>Specialization: Comparative genomics</p>	<p>Organization: University of Melbourne</p> <p>Gender: Female</p> <p>Specialization: Bioinformatics and evolutionary biology</p>	<p>Organization: University of Queensland Coast</p> <p>Gender: Male</p> <p>Specialization: Bioinformatics Workflow building</p>	<p>Organization: University of the Sunshine Coast</p> <p>Gender: Female</p> <p>Specialization: Chemistry and Microbiology</p>

Key Insights & Themes

Pain Points

1. Galaxy tools create **pain points** across the research life cycle

- At the **planning stage**, there is missing tools, this leads to the user being unsure of whether their tool of interest can be installed on Galaxy. This often will require the tools team to look into the matter and this creates a time lag and uncertainty for the user as to whether this is a feasible option.
- At the **process stage**, there are issues with tool search, with a user stating that tool search is broken. Additionally there is a concern older tools will not be compatible with modern data. Tools often just didn't work or were broken. One user also stated an unsupported file type led them to have to convert the file using a tool outside of Galaxy and then port it back into Galaxy.

- At the **analyze stage**, users reported issues with memory limits associated with tools, tools not working as expected and having to troubleshoot, error messages not being clear as to why the tool has failed. Additionally unavailability of certain tools was reported as an issue at this stage as well.

2. Galaxy histories are creating **pain points** at the **analyze stage**.

- Issue with selecting the wrong data from the history, therefore getting a result that is wrong and this confusing the user.
- Also if a user doesn't rename files in their history it can get very messy and confusing. Additionally, if a tool accept multiple different file types from their history this can be confusing for the user.
- It was noted "File naming conventions are a steep learning curve for people.
- Another user remarked "history outputs are not intuitive".
- Error messages were noted to not be intuitive or explanatory for users, meaning they have to spend longer reading and re-reading the messages to figure out what is happening.
- A user commented they *hated* that there was no estimated progress time indication in the history panel for how long a job will take to complete.

3. Issues relating to data discovery, data storage and reproducibility are creating **pain points** for users across the research life cycle.

- At the **planning stage**, data size, data transfer/movement and security issues were listed as concerns. Additionally there are reported blockers is obtaining resources, with researchers not knowing who to contact about obtaining resources.
- At the **collecting stage**, there were pain points reported with raw sequencing data, in that the file size was large, therefore moving from the provider to Cloudstor and then to Galaxy was difficult. Discovery was a reported issue, with users not being able to find data on repos due to their structure, Databases not being accessible on Galaxy and therefore having to import them and downtime waiting for metadata for be available. Additionally when users needed to import external datasets into Galaxy, a lot of the existing tools to do so were broken.
- At the **process stage**, a user reported that sequencing providers do not provide enough information about the data, for example whether the adapter sequence is included in the read sequence, barcodes and read header.
- At the **preserve stage**, users reported finding storage can be challenging, data taking up space on their computer if downloaded locally, and that they would only keep small datasets on Galaxy, for example only basecall data, not raw nanopore data.
- At the **share stage**, re-analysis of data is a pain point and this includes mistakes in the analysis that now need to be fixed, recollecting result data, and a review process that can require major or minor revisions in the context of publishing

findings. Additionally, downloading data and exporting via a home network was a pain point, along with limited options to share data within Galaxy. Finally, some repos were reported as clunky for sharing data, particularly NCBI.

- At the **preserve stage**, issues with file formatting and reproducibility were reported. Incompatibility of file formats with software, needing extensive tooling for converting file formats, and file corruption were stated. Additionally, missing data and challenges relating to reusing and reproducing analysis in a C+VM and NCI environment because tools have to be re-installed and the environment setup again.

Opportunities

1. The Galaxy tools as a broad feature set presents a great opportunity to improve the UI/UX, functionality and processes behind provisioning this widely used component of Galaxy.

Opportunities from users

- “Can we optimize what tools we prioritize to wrap. Can we crowdsource this information somehow to inform us?”
- “Lag in new tools being available for researchers - how could we improve the pipeline for incorporating latest tools and suites.”
- “Proactive approach to identifying and wrapping very current tools.”
- “Tool wrapping could use more resourcing.”
- “I might read about tools that have been included in a published paper, I might want to use this next. In an ideal world the tools team would have bandwidth and resources to wrap these tools faster.”
- “I want to know a set of tools that work together and if they actually work with modern data. Early technologies are much smaller and didnt scale well. I wanted to know if it s compatible with phython object (ANNdata) I wanted to see the scampy tools. It was confusing to discern this.”
- “How can we incorporate licensed products into Galaxy?”
- “Broken tools - huge opportunity to fix or remove broken tools. This will create a lot of value for researchers, we will create more goodwill and this is one of the first impression they have of the service.”
- “Tool browser that works outside of the tool menu, too small real estate.”

Questions

How can we be more efficient in the tools we choose to wrap? What process do we use currently to prioritize this?

How do we ascertain what tools are important to the community currently? What is the process?

Recommendations

- Include more metadata on tools, this will provide the user with more information and improve trust. Additionally, crowdsourced metadata from Galaxy users such as a 5 star rating on tool pages, or a user comment section could allow users to provide feedback and assist each other in real time. This opportunity will require further brainstorming.
- Review and reimagine the Toolshed UX, it currently appears disconnected, i.e. the toolshed is not discoverable through the tool panel and the importing function is not straight forward.
- Create more robust mechanisms for capturing feedback on existing tools and new tools suggested to be wrapped.
- Identify ways to resource more rapid tool wrapping, or explore ways to automate or decentralize the process.
- Identify and fix or remove all broken tools currently supported on Galaxy Australia.
- Fix tools search to improve tool discovery and reduce pain points for users.
- Review all tool related error messages to ensure they clearly communicate the error, therefore reducing troubleshooting time for the user and lowering support request that could have been solved with better error messages.

2. Galaxy histories, continues to present pain points for users, despite a large update to the history UI last year. This is mainly occurring when researchers need to analyze their data in Galaxy.

Opportunities from users

- “I wish there was a way to mark histories with a do not delete tag, for example datasets for published Galaxy tutorials, I wish the deletion wasn't so automatic.”
- “It would be nice if Galaxy could allow for upload data and it could covert into submission formats. There are roughly 100 metadata fields that have to be filled out for submission, so it would be great if Galaxy could produce a report of what tools, versions, data was used in analysis. Upload straight from Galaxy even.”
- “Improving how the UI communicates why something has gone wrong.”

Recommendations

- I recommend usability testing the Galaxy history UI/UX to gather more targeted feedback on where users are experiencing pain points.

- Reviewing file naming conventions, is it intuitive?
- Reviewing all history error messages, how can they be improved?
- Explore the UX of estimated time progress in the history panel for how long a job will take to complete.

3. Data discovery, data analysis, data storage and data reproducibility represent the backbone of Galaxy's core offering. Below are outlined opportunities to improve on this core competency.

Opportunities from users

- Data transfer - making it more seamless. Authentication standardization helps with this.
- "Having an Australia based repo intermediate between open and private - it may be easier for large datasets from overseas for file transfer, or for people who need to share datasets between consortia where they dont want it to be open access, a way to make some data private."
- "Bioplatforms has a close relationship with sequencing data providers in Australia, we could standardize how information is provisioned for raw data interpretation."
- "Opportunity to inform researchers on know how for interpreting sequencing data."
- Use of Rsync may improve this process (data transfer).
- "Biocommons - centralize resources for easy discovery"
- "If the biocommons website could include more information for certain database (reference genome and other genomic data as well). For public databases that the bionformatician is incoportating into their workflow."
- "Process improvement - talk to supervisor to contact Biocommons to locate and source resources. This could also potentially be a webpage"
- "Big opportunity for researchers to do basecalling with new models relevant for particular species. Galaxy would need a lot of computational configuration."
- "I imagine doing pre-analysis work in Galaxy and then pulling into R."
- "Galaxy is limited to genomic data and is mainly used for this purpose. Opportunity to expand the domains in which Galaxy services."

Recommendations

- Reimagine the Biocommons UI/UX of the website to service researchers material needs more clearly and centralize resources. "If I need x then do y". <https://fitzroyacademy.com/> Is a UI example I have in mind.
- Data standardization across sequencing providers, platforms and online repos. Can standardization for data transfer and sharing be done? If not, why not? What are the blockers?

User Journey Mapping Findings

	Jobs to be done	Context and touchpoints	Pains	Opportunities	Emotion
Planning	<p>Client interaction took up a large volume of responses in relation to jobs to be done. This included getting the client to specifically define the problem and hypothesis, assess whether the project had been done before and identifying what data and samples needed to be collected.</p> <p>Additionally, conducting a literature review was also reported.</p>	<p>Human touch points</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-supervisor • Principal supervisor • PhD student • Biologist • Researcher • Jnr Bioinformatician • Senior Bioinformatician <p>Technology touchpoints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Outlook • Zoom • Teams • Galaxy Australia • QCIF (RCC) 	<p>Galaxy tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Missing tools. • “Not being sure whether these tools could be installed on Galaxy easily. This is unknown until the tools team can take a look at it. This can cause a time lag in and there is a unknown in how long this could take.” <p>Information Asymmetries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not knowing who to contact for help or resources • “Sometimes time estimations can be without all the information.” • Understanding what client wants • Uncertainty around specifics of methods <p>Data & resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data size 	<p>Galaxy Tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Proactive approach to identifying and wrapping very current tools.” • “I might read about tools that have been included in a published paper, I might want to use this next. In an ideal world the tools team would have bandwidth and resources to wrap these tools faster.” • “Can we optimize what tools we prioritize to wrap. Can we crowdsource this information somehow to inform us?” <p>Information Discovery</p>	<p>Negative emotions</p> <p>Cautious</p> <p>Daunting</p> <p>Uncertainty</p> <p>Positive Emotions</p> <p>Optimistic</p> <p>Fun</p> <p>Motivated</p> <p>Helpful</p> <p>Excitement</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National infrastructure (Galaxy or NCI). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data transferring/movement. Blocker is obtaining resources Security issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biocommons - centralize resources for easy discovery 	
	Jobs to be done 	Context and touchpoints 	Pains	Opportunities	Emotion
Collecting	<p>Dry lab work was the main theme here, with respondents stating they receive and download raw data from sequencing facilities, collect metadata from client, and access existing data to compare to the data they have received.</p> <p>Resourcing was reported, where application for compute resources starts at this point.</p> <p>Wet lab work was also reported, which included extraction and making media to grow things like bacteria and fungi</p>	<p>Data Repositories</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> NCBI <p>Sequencing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> AGRF Sequencing facility Ramaciotti Diversigen <p>Storage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> University storage facilities University server RDM USB OneDrive 	<p>Data discovery and retrieval</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Raw sequencing data - pain point is with size of the file. sequencing provider > cloudstor > Galaxy I tested this a year ago and it was difficult.” “Not being able to find the data - issue with structure of other repos.” “Downtime waiting for information or metadata to be available.” “Importing other, external datasets using the existing tools, a lot the tools are broken for completing this step.” 	<p>Data transfer</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data transfer - making it more seamless. Authentication standardization helps with this. Use of Rsync may improve this process. <p>Information Discovery</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “If the biocommons website could include more information for certain database (reference genome and other genomic 	<p>Negative emotions</p> <p>Occasional Frustration</p> <p>If it works, exciting, if not deterring and disappointing</p> <p>Frustration</p> <p>Overwhelming</p> <p>Neutral emotions</p> <p>Neutral</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Griffith Owncloud <p>Human touchpoints</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The researcher /client Supervisors <p>Lab work</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Working with whenever the data is stored, I don't get to choose this, therefore I have to adapt.” “Either database is not available on Galaxy or we have to find it externally” <p>Versioning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tool versioning Reference genome versioning <p>Lab</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contamination issues Experiments not working out <p>Annotation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annotation usually needs refinement. <p>Human</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication with the researcher. “Quite often we are not on the 	<p>data as well). For public databases that the bioinformatician is incorporating into their workflow.”</p> <p>Galaxy tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> “Broken tools - huge opportunity to fix or remove broken tools. This will create a lot of value for researchers, we will create more goodwill and this is one of the first impressions they have of the service.” 	<p>Less emotion</p> <p>Positive emotions</p> <p>Productive</p>
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			same page and won't match my understanding of something."		
	Jobs to be done 	Context and touchpoints 	Pains	Opportunities	Emotion
Process	<p>Once again dry lab work was common at this step. This included uploading and QC of data, checking annotations, data cleaning, looking up trimming tools in Galaxy, and then trimming data.</p> <p>Resourcing and setting up one's environment was another job which included setting up Rstudio and installing packages, setting up an analysis directory, doing compute on local machines, Rstudio server and client resources.</p>	<p>Galaxy Australia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tools • QC • Data analysis <p>Virtual Machines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nectar • NCI machine • Servers • HPC • University supported machines <p>R</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R studio • Workflow R 	<p>Galaxy tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Tools don't work but not as common as previous step." • "Search is broken with tools, was searching single cell tools and there are tools that work together. I want to know a set of tools that work together and if they actually work with modern data. Early technologies are much smaller and didnt scale well. I wanted to know if it s compatible with phython object (ANNdata) I wanted to see the scampy tools. It was confusing to discern this." 	<p>UI/UX</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "Geneious had colours to indicate a good or bad sequence and what parts you may want trim." • "You can see it visually and you can see where its not clean and uses a colour indicator for this." <p>Galaxy tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • "I want to know a set of tools that work together and if they actually work 	<p>Negative emotions</p> <p>Frustrating Confusion</p> <p>Neutral emotions</p> <p>Neutral</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QCIF Rstudio serve 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “You had executed the tool but the output in the history panel didnt produce the expected result. Not enough feedback as to why. It wasnt clear what the steps were involved to complete the process.” • “File type AB1, Galaxy didnt support this filetype, I had to find a conversion tool outside of Galaxy. This successfully converted to the needed file type.” • “You'd been trying to trim the file and were finding it confusing.” <p>VM Environments</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Using NCI can lead to downtime and less flexibility with tool installation.” • “Plain VM might not have a powerful cluster attached to the machine. Not 	<p>with modern data. Early technologies are much smaller and didnt scale well. I wanted to know if it s compatible with phython object (ANNdata) I wanted to see the scampy tools. It was confusing to discern this.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Tool browser that works outside of the tool menu, too small real estate.” <p>Galaxy features</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Big opportunity for researchers to do basecalling with new models relevant for particular species. Galaxy would need a lot 	
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			<p>comparable to NCI high performing machine.”</p> <p>Sequencing</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Sometimes files from sequencing provider they don't provide enough information - whether the adapter sequence is included in the read sequence, barcodes, and read header.” 	<p>of computational configuration.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “I imagine doing pre-analysis work in Galaxy and then pulling into R.” <p>Information discovery</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Bioplatforms has a close relationship with sequencing data providers in Australia, we could standardize how information is provisioned for raw data interpretation.” • “Opportunity to inform researchers on know how for interpreting sequencing data.” • “Process improvement - talk to supervisor 	
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				to contact Biocommons to locate and source resources. This could also potentially be a webpage”	
	Jobs to be done 	Context and touchpoints 	Pains	Opportunities	Emotion
Analyse	The major themes here are divided into two categories Galaxy based tasks and non-Galaxy based tasks. This included creating a Galaxy account, moving data into Galaxy, finding an appropriate tool for data processing, building and testing workflows, checking correct versioning on tools, genome assembly, and making a tool request to Galaxy Australia if the tool is not there.	Galaxy Australia <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tutorials • Data analysis QCIF training calendar Storage <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nectar VMs • Local PC • Institute network Software <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geneious 	Galaxy Tools <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Particular tools have memory limits and when you are trying to use Galaxy for larger data, the job will error out and you'll be reading the error and you are thinking what is this error? But really the memory has just timed out because it is not enough. The you have to submit and report the error to someone. <p>If I had submitted the job and it alerted this to me before that would</p>	Galaxy Australia <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Galaxy is limited to genomic data and is mainly used for this purpose. Opportunity to expand the domains in which Galaxy services.” • “How can we incorporate licensed products into Galaxy?” • “I can see Galaxy being useful for pre-processing of single cell data.” 	Negative emotions <p>Frustration</p> <p>Anxiety</p> <p>Confusion</p> <p>Tedious</p> <p>Challenging</p> Positive Emotions <p>Fun</p> <p>Trust</p>

	<p>Alternatively to Galaxy respondents reported conducting analysis-differential expression, download extensions (software package) from Geneious and using the consensus sequence Blast search in Geneious using NCBI.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rstudio • PhymI 	<p>save me a lot of time. I would then just email support for memory.</p> <p>repetitive issues.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Tool fails <p>Investigating if it's the tool or infrastructure, problem or issue with data - troubleshooting.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Tools not working as expected (error) this could also be an issue with how the user is inputting data or what data is being inputted.” • “A person was running a tool and it was giving an error. I re-ran in history and it gave them a different output. I then referred this issue on to the support admin, I told them how to do this through Galaxy. (submit a report)” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Someway of automating data check to ensure that certain tools will run. (Gareth's idea)” • “Improving how the UI communicates why something has gone wrong.” 	
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			<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Missing reference genome tool not being available.• "I am trying to run this tool but its not working, it will be the wrong data. Sometimes Galaxy has data prompts for input and they'd selected the wrong data from their history." <p>Galaxy History</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• "I dont like how you cant tell how far your job is when it is running. No progress indication, is this going to be days? hours? I really hate that there is no indication of how long this will take."• "History outputs are not intuitive."• "Error messages are not very explanatory or detailed and it can take a while to read and re-read to figure out exactly what the error		
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			<p>is and what the issue is.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “File naming conventions is a steep learning curve for people.” • “If the user hasn't renamed files in history very well it can get messy. If a tool accepts 3 different file types in their history it can confused.” 		
	Jobs to be done 	Context and touchpoints 	Pains	Opportunities	Emotion
Preserve	<p>Online repos were the most popular reported method of preserving data. One respondent stated “I don't want to store it myself, locally or in the cloud. Because I might lose access so I like it to be in an open access repo so I find and retrieve it easily. This helps with versioning as well.”</p>	<p>Galaxy Australia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short term storage (up to 12 months) <p>Local Storage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • USB <p>Institutional Storage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OneDrive 	<p>Storage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “I wouldn't keep raw nanopore data (on Galaxy) and only keep basecall data which is much smaller.” • “Taking up space on my computer if downloaded locally.” • “Finding own storage” <p>Galaxy Notifications</p>	<p>Galaxy Australia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “I wish there was a way to mark histories with a do not delete tag, for example datasets for published Galaxy tutorials, I wish the deletion wasnt so automatic.” • “It would be nice if Galaxy could 	<p>Negative emotions</p> <p>Frustration</p> <p>Stress</p> <p>Neutral emotions</p> <p>Neutral</p>

	<p>Other responses included Institutional and local storage, while also stating it can also depend on where the client wants to store the data.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • R drive <p>Online repos</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SRA database • NCBI • Zenodo 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Things get earmarked for deletion after 12 months. I'm receiving emails almost everyday for histories that are being deleted, thats taking up my cognitive load to address this constantly.” 	<p>allow for upload data and it could covert into submission formats. There are roughly 100 metadata fields that have to be filled out for submission, so it would be great if Galaxy could produce a report of what tools, versions, data was used in analysis. Upload straight from Galaxy even.”</p> <p>Information discovery</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Explain more option in the life cycle for where bioinformaticians can preserve” 	
	<p>Jobs to be done </p>	<p>Context and touchpoints </p>	<p>Pains </p>	<p>Opportunities </p>	<p>Emotion </p>

<p>Share</p>	<p>Major theme here is handover to the researcher/client. This involves compiling all datasets and files with explanation of how they were made, and links to workflows and directories</p>	<p>Galaxy Australia</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Share history within Galaxy with the client. <p>Institutional Storage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cloudstor • Griffith owncloud <p>R</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WorkflowR • Rstudio <p>Online journals and repos</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online open access repo • MDPI journal 	<p>Re-analysis of data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Mistakes in analysis and they now need to be fixed.” • “Annoying bit is recollecting result data.” • “Review process can require major or minor revisions. This can sometimes add considerable time.” <p>Galaxy</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “At UQ we RDM and QCIF infrastructure RDM is a dataportal built by UQ, RCC is looking after infrastructure (high performance machine.) Galaxy can't connect to this at the moment” • “Galaxy has limited options to share data.” <p>Local & Online Repos</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Downloading data and exporting data via the 	<p>Negative Emotions</p> <p>Frustration</p> <p>Tired</p> <p>Nervous</p> <p>Neutral Emotions</p> <p>Neutral</p> <p>Positive Emotions</p> <p>Excitement</p> <p>Social</p>
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		Email Supervisor	<p>home network is a pain point.”</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Some of the repos are clunky, particularly NCBI, uploading sequencing data is terrible. Documents and files is straight forward.” 		
	Jobs to be done 	Context and touchpoints 	Pains	Opportunities	Emotion
Reuse	<p>The three main areas for reusing data were Galaxy Australia, online repos and singularity containers.</p> <p>Respondents said they used Galaxy because All the databases, data, tool versions,reference data, and workflows are there and you can reproduce this analysis.</p>	<p>Galaxy Australia</p> <p>Institutional Storage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Singularity containers • VMs • NCI • Cloudstor <p>Online repos</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NCBI • Journal - hosting the publication 	<p>File formatting</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “File formats not compatible with the software I am using.” • “Need extensive access to tools for converting files formats.” • File corruption <p>Reproducibility</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Missing data • “Finding out I didn't upload it or a component of it to open access” 	<p>Galaxy tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Lag in new tools being available for researchers - how could we improve the pipeline for incorporating latest tools and suites.” • “Tool wrapping could use more resourcing.” <p>Data storage</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Having an Australia based 	<p>Negative Emotions</p> <p>Tedious</p> <p>Annoyance</p> <p>Positive Emotions</p> <p>Productive</p> <p>Happy</p> <p>Relief</p> <p>Motivation</p>

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • open access portal <p>Lab book - it is a physical lab, not digitized</p> <p>Geo</p> <p>10X</p> <p>Local storage</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Not everything is covered in a publication, not going to report stuff that doesn't work. Some things are left out and that can affect reproducibility.” • “More challenging to reuse or reproduce analysis in VM or NCI because you have to re-install tools and setup the environment again.” 	<p>repo intermediate between open and private - it may be easier for large datasets from overseas for file transfer, or for people who need to share datasets between consortia where they dont want it to be open access, a way to make some data private.”</p>	
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Galaxy UX questionnaire feedback

What gender do you identify with?

What age category best describes you?

Which of these resources do you access for your research?

Personas

FATIMA FAHEEM

Gender : Female
Age : 40
Education : PhD
Job : Bioinformatician

BIOGRAPHY

Fatima is a bioinformatician, embedded in a Australian university institute. She works with clients to analyse data, develop tools and bioinformatics workflows for Galaxy Australia and uses R studio and R markdown. A lot of the how and what of her everyday is dictated by client requirements, thus she works closely with researchers to understand their goals and needs in relation to project work. She exclusively works dry lab and spends her days on her computer. She occasionally participates in running training workshops to upskill researchers, other bioinformaticians and the broader life science community.

GOALS

Assemble genomes

Generally, I provide Bioinformatic supports to the researchers, so my goals are based on the researchers' goals at the moment.

Author more tools and bioinformatics workflows for Galaxy

MOTIVATIONS

I enjoy the variety of work and data.

Bioinformatics combines both biology and tech

Find out about genomes and therefore about biology (function, development, ecology).

HOW WOULD YOU RATE YOUR COMFORT WITH PLATFORM-BASED RESEARCH TOOLS (LIKE GENBANK OR GALAXY)?

FRUSTRATIONS

Time constraints, resourcing.

Handling multiple tasks simultaneously and it's not always clear what tasks to prioritize

In the bioinformatics world, insufficient resources (ie. CPU/Memory/Storage) stop researchers to achieve their goals.

A big challenge is finding the best way to visualize results.

WHICH OF THESE RESOURCES DO YOU ACCESS FOR YOUR RESEARCH?

JESSICA DAVIS

Gender : Female
Age : 45
Education : PhD
Job : E-research Analyst

BIOGRAPHY

Jessica is an e-research Analyst for a tertiary institute. She is a trained bioinformatician and her job is to assist researchers in navigating their research life cycle, from accessing compute resources, to troubleshooting bioinformatics platforms like Galaxy Australia. Jessica helps researchers upload, analyze and store their data. She also provisions training materials to upskill researchers. She does not conduct her own research in this role.

GOALS

Helping people. Ideally more research will get done if I can make support easier to obtain

Assisting researchers to make the best use of technologies

MOTIVATIONS

I like the diversity of topics and questions, somedays people will ask how do I do something in Galaxy? Or I want to do this in R, this code isn't working though can you help me? Everyday something different.

Helping people. Ideally more research will get done if I can make support easier to obtain

HOW WOULD YOU RATE YOUR COMFORT WITH PLATFORM-BASED RESEARCH TOOLS (LIKE GENBANK OR GALAXY)?

FRUSTRATIONS

There seems to be a lot of scattered support for researchers and I'm having trouble getting my head around it all.

It can be dependent on people needing my help. I might not get to troubleshoot or help someone on a particular day because no one has asked for help. Sometimes there is inconsistency in requests.

WHICH OF THESE RESOURCES DO YOU ACCESS FOR YOUR RESEARCH?

TOMMY CHEN

Gender : Male
Age : 28
Education : Masters
Job : PhD Student

BIOGRAPHY

Tommy is a PhD student, specializing in complex biosynthesis and small molecule chemistry. His tasks include reading research papers, analyzing data, generating figures, writing or editing code. Additionally, he plans experiments and supervises undergraduates. He reports to a principal supervisor.

GOALS

Complete my PhD for publication, and be published in a reputable journal

Learning new techniques, getting better at coding, understanding processes for accessing and configuring resources

Immersing myself in the scientific community within Australia and be able to present findings at conferences.

Be hired for a postdoc position

My research goals is to find something in the environment we can utilise for the society. That's being either sunscreens, pharmaceuticals etc.

MOTIVATIONS

The science. Figuring new things out and how the world works fascinates me.

The process of discovery with lab work.

These goals are important to enhance the bioeconomy of Australia and the World, and to improve the life of humans

I enjoy research, to complete my PhD and get a good position once I finish

HOW WOULD YOU RATE YOUR COMFORT WITH PLATFORM-BASED RESEARCH TOOLS (LIKE GENBANK OR GALAXY)?

FRUSTRATIONS

My PhD can be stressful and anxiety inducing. Academia can be quite challenging with grant writing and the pressure to publish papers.

It is frustrating when experiments fail and you have to redo lab and/or analysis work.

Lack of advanced python coding skills, general lack of self-confidence, uni computers not letting me be a damn administrator and change installations easily

Lack of resources and lack of support

Computational power. It's hard to do these things without having the computational power needed. Further, platforms like Galaxy does not provide me with all the pipelines.

WHICH OF THESE RESOURCES DO YOU ACCESS FOR YOUR RESEARCH?